

Gravity and Mass in Euclidean Space

Postvaikin Pavel Evgrafovich

2025.11.23

Abstract

This work is devoted to investigating the possibility of constructing a model of masses, momentum propagation, and the emergence of gravitational effects in three-dimensional Euclidean space \mathbb{R}^3 : whether vectors and their chaotic motion can reproduce effects similar to gravity and form structures stable in volume and time with a minimal set of physical assumptions.

1 Introduction

1.1 Model Construction Principle

We construct a model of matter behavior in 3-dimensional Euclidean space. Matter does not disappear or appear - the total quantity remains unchanged. Also, momentum - the average velocity vector possessed by a selected portion of matter - does not disappear or appear from nowhere.

Matter consists of infinitely small and infinitely divisible number-vectors that always move with the only possible speed modulus $|\mathbf{v}|$ in all directions. All space is completely filled with such matter, and the density of matter in a selected volume can be any starting from infinitely close to zero.

1.2 Collisions

Matter collides in motion continuously with surrounding matter. At each point in space, matter enters from all directions simultaneously, colliding at the point, and redistributes along all directions of vectors $|\mathbf{v}|$. In any infinitely small volume, an infinite number of collisions will occur.

The exit from any infinitely small region of space (from a point) is the result of adding all the number-vectors that entered this region at the moment of collision, having speed modulus $|\mathbf{v}|$. The amount of matter that entered the collision point is preserved when exiting the point. And the total impulse-vector of all matter that entered the collision point is preserved. The exit from each collision of vectors will be an uneven distribution of matter in all directions - along all vectors with modulus $|\mathbf{v}|$, exiting from the collision point and preserving the total momentum of all collided matter.

Thus, for example, each number-vector can be scattered uniformly in all directions only by an equal and oppositely directed number-vector. The result of such a collision will be a symmetric sphere of vectors $|\mathbf{v}|$.

Infinitely divisible and space-filling matter changes direction of motion, infinitely dividing and mixing with oncoming matter. The separation of matter into centers of exit

from collisions and differential fluctuations at a given density is the result of the geometric impossibility of filling space with identical spheres at any scale of fragmentation and, as a consequence, the difference in oncoming vectors in magnitude and direction. If we imagine an initially completely balanced medium where at each point in space the amount of matter is the same and vectors are uniformly distributed in all directions, that is, an analogy of heat death, then at the next moment collisions of spheres of vectors exiting from all points in space will occur. This makes the emergence of fluctuations inevitable and leads to non-uniform distribution of matter along vectors as a result of subsequent collisions and uneven density of matter in extremely small regions of space. The "height" of such waves should be related to the density of matter in space.

1.3 Displacement

In any infinitely small bounded region of space, all possible vectors of matter exist in all directions. Matter is distributed unevenly among them, and for such a region there is a total momentum. In a selected region of space, we can distinguish the amount of matter not moving on average in space (the sum of these vectors equals 0) and distinguish the amount of matter moving through this region of space, and the average direction of motion of this matter and the average speed of this movement (i.e., momentum).

At a fixed moment in time, all vectors of moving matter will be located in the hemisphere of vectors with positive coordinate along the momentum motion axis in this region of space, but they will collide with all matter in this region of space and the average speed of momentum motion is calculated from the total amount of matter.

If another momentum carried by matter with a different distribution along vectors enters a region of space having some distribution of matter along vectors, then the amount of matter and their distributions are summed as a result of collisions.

By isolating and excluding the average amount of non-moving matter (sum of vectors equals 0), we obtain in this region the amount of matter with average speed in the direction of the total momentum, which in modulus will be less than the modulus of the average speed of the faster momentum before addition.

Thus, a locally existing momentum when moving through the medium will lose its speed relative to the average speed of this medium, while increasing the amount of matter moving in its direction. At the same time, the existing momentum in the region of space is preserved.

1.4 Waves

When moving through a stationary medium with the same distribution of matter along vectors in all regions of space, a plane homogeneous momentum wave or a radially symmetric spherical wave will maintain its speed. Entering a layer of matter not affected by the wave, the matter of the wave mixes with the matter of the medium. Addition over the entire wave surface will occur symmetrically. The momentum of the wave will be distributed along vectors to the total amount of matter in the region of space through which the wave is moving at the moment.

A wave in space will propagate as a front of matter pressure and move with speed from 0 to $|\mathbf{v}|/2$, since $|\mathbf{v}|/2$ is the mathematical average speed of a hemisphere of vectors with radius $|\mathbf{v}|$ in any selected direction.

The matter vector normal to the wave front will collide with the medium first, immediately scattering along the sphere of vectors and transferring its momentum to the oncoming matter. Other vectors of the wave front will also collide with the matter of the medium and with the matter of the wave front. A momentum moving in space, entering a denser medium, will increase the amount of matter in its wave so that part of the distribution matter exceeding the speed-balanced part will have an average speed $|\mathbf{v}|/2$ as a result of collisions and will reduce speed until merging with the wave, increasing the amount of involved matter. Similarly, exiting from a denser medium to a less dense one, the wave will carry its momentum with a smaller amount of matter at a higher speed, stretching its length when exiting into lower density.

Thus, the momentum of the wave will be carried by the amount of matter corresponding to the maximum speed of movement in a medium with such density of matter. The speed $|\mathbf{v}|/2$ can be approached by the wave only in extremely "empty" space.

2 Modeling Matter Interactions

2.1 Matter and Density

We consider three-dimensional Euclidean space \mathbb{R}^3 with coordinates $\mathbf{r} = (x, y, z)$. Matter represents a vector numerical value contained in a region of space, and in each region of space there is matter whose volume density ρ_V is measured in $\left(\frac{\text{Amount of matter}}{(\text{Unit of distance})^3}\right)$ or $[\mathbf{m}/l^3]$.

Each infinitely small element \mathbf{m} can be characterized by only two polar coordinates of the vector \mathbf{v} , whose modulus is $|\mathbf{v}| = 1$. And the amount \mathbf{m} in a differentially small volume of space is already a numerical value of quantity and two polar coordinates of the vector \mathbf{v} .

From this point onward, we assume $|\mathbf{v}| = 1 \left(\frac{\text{Unit of distance}}{\text{Unit of time}}\right) = 1[l/t]$ and simultaneously accept: the unit of time is determined by the length of the full trajectory of any portion of matter over the observation period. Each infinitely small portion moves with the only possible speed modulus $|\mathbf{v}| = 1$, but propagates in space as a differentially small sector of the sphere surface $r = |\mathbf{1}|t$.

Linear density ρ is a quantity measured in $\left(\frac{\text{Amount of matter}}{\text{Unit of distance}}\right)$, which describes the amount of matter along a straight line - a characteristic of continuous and variable distribution of matter in space in one dimension. Linear density in three dimensions "transforms" into volume density by raising to the third power $\rho_V = (\rho^3)$. Linear density in our model is not an analogy of linear density accepted in standard physics.

The linear density ρ of matter in space determines the averaged "collision frequency" on the path of any portion of matter, or otherwise: the average path distance until complete scattering of the initial momentum of the observed matter by oncoming matter flows against the general background of fluctuations in this density ρ .

The total amount of matter in any volume V is calculated through the integral:

$$M_{\mathbf{m}} = \int_V \rho^3 d^3r.$$

Here d^3r is the volume element, and the integral sums the density over the entire region V . $M_{\mathbf{m}}$ is a scalar quantity - the amount of matter in the selected volume. For example: doubling the amount of matter $2 \cdot M_{\mathbf{m}}$ is equivalent to increasing ρ by $(2^{1/3})$ times.

There is a vector field of momentum of this matter $\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{r}, t)$. The magnitude of this field corresponds to the product of the volume density of matter $\rho_V = \rho^3(\mathbf{r}, t)$ and the

vector sum of velocities of all matter in this differential volume of space. The direction indicates where the matter collectively moves at this point at time t .

When two flows collide, matter mixes, preserving the total quantity and momentum, after which it continues moving until the next collision in the form of a spherical uneven distribution in all directions.

Consider what happens when two matter flows, denoted as $\mathbf{P}_1 = \rho_1^3 \mathbf{v}_1 \Delta V$ and $\mathbf{P}_2 = \rho_2^3 \mathbf{v}_2 \Delta V$, collide in the region ΔV of point \mathbf{r}_0 at time t_0 . Here ρ_1 and ρ_2 are the flow densities, \mathbf{v}_1 and \mathbf{v}_2 are their directions of motion ($|\vec{v}_1| = |\vec{v}_2| = 1$), and ΔV is an extremely small volume.

During collision, two conservation laws are fulfilled:

Conservation of matter: The total amount of matter after collision equals the sum before collision:

$$M = |\mathbf{M}_1| + |\mathbf{M}_2| = \rho_1^3 \Delta V + \rho_2^3 \Delta V.$$

Conservation of momentum: Momentum is a vector quantity depending on the amount of matter and its motion:

$$\mathbf{P} = \mathbf{P}_1 + \mathbf{P}_2 = \rho_1^3 \mathbf{v}_1 \Delta V + \rho_2^3 \mathbf{v}_2 \Delta V.$$

For the general case of arbitrary directions of colliding matter vectors with quantities $|\mathbf{M}_1|$, $|\mathbf{M}_2|$, the following formula for the exit distribution from collision is proposed:

$$\sigma(\vec{n}, t) = \frac{M}{4\pi[v(t-t_0)]^2} \cdot \frac{|\beta|}{4\pi \sinh |\beta|} \cdot e^{\vec{\beta} \cdot \vec{n}},$$

where $\vec{\beta}$ is the vector anisotropy parameter; $|\beta| = \sqrt{\vec{\beta} \cdot \vec{\beta}}$ is the norm of vector $\vec{\beta}$.

The direction $\vec{\beta}$ is determined from the momentum conservation condition $M = m_1 + m_2$; $v(t-t_0) = R$ is the propagation sphere radius.

The vector parameter $\vec{\beta}$ is determined from the equation:

$$L(|\beta|) \cdot \frac{\vec{\beta}}{|\beta|} = \frac{\vec{P}}{M},$$

where $L(x) = (\coth x - \frac{1}{x})$ is the Langevin function, and $\vec{P} = m_1 \vec{v}_1 + m_2 \vec{v}_2$ is the resulting momentum.

Verification of matter conservation:

$$\int \sigma(\vec{n}, t) dS = \frac{M}{4\pi R^2} \cdot \frac{|\beta|}{4\pi \sinh |\beta|} \int e^{\vec{\beta} \cdot \vec{n}} R^2 d\Omega = M.$$

The normalization factor $\frac{|\beta|}{4\pi \sinh |\beta|}$ ensures fulfillment of the matter conservation law.

Momentum conservation:

$$\int \vec{n} \sigma(\vec{n}, t) dS = \frac{M}{4\pi R^2} \cdot \frac{|\beta|}{4\pi \sinh |\beta|} \int \vec{n} e^{\vec{\beta} \cdot \vec{n}} R^2 d\Omega = M \cdot L(|\beta|) \cdot \frac{\vec{\beta}}{|\beta|}.$$

From the definition of parameter $\vec{\beta}$ it follows that $L(|\beta|) \cdot \frac{\vec{\beta}}{|\beta|} = \frac{\vec{P}}{M}$, therefore:

$$\int \vec{n} \sigma(\vec{n}, t) dS = M \cdot \frac{\vec{P}}{M} = \vec{P}.$$

Thus, the momentum conservation law is exactly fulfilled.

The proposed model provides a consistent and mathematically correct description of the collision and redistribution process of matter for arbitrary directions of matter vectors. This is a hypothesis based on the assumption that this would be the exit of matter from a limited region of extremely small space after an infinite number of collisions and mixings in it with the condition of conservation of matter and momentum inside.

2.2 Motion of a Selected Portion of Matter

After collision, matter tends to propagate in the form of a spherical wave front, which is a natural consequence of its distribution in all directions with constant speed $|\mathbf{v}| = 1$. The spherical exit collides with surrounding matter. Each such collision leads to division and mixing of matter, changing its direction of motion randomly. For a selected volume of space, collisions inside it lead to matter spreading beyond its boundaries, and density decreases if the density outside is lower.

The total momentum of a region of space does not continue to move as a single whole in one direction. Since the basic elements of matter can move in any direction with speed $|\mathbf{1}|$, the resulting momentum is redistributed among many new elementary vectors emanating from the collision point. This process of continuous mixing and redistribution leads to any localized momentum or density cluster not remaining static but having a tendency to expand. The front carrying this momentum will propagate in space like a wave.

Despite the fact that matter vectors move with fundamental speed $|\mathbf{v}|$, the maximum speed v at which any stable matter cluster or total momentum of a region of space can move as a single wave process is limited by the value $v = |\mathbf{v}|/2$. This limitation is a consequence of the nature of space, collisions, and interactions between matter.

2.3 Random Walks

First, imagine movement along nodes of a three-dimensional lattice of volume 1 with speed $|\mathbf{v}| = 1$, in which $(N)^3$ intersections are located. In statistics, it is proven that in space of volume 1 with step between lattice nodes $(1/N)$, the path of a random walk from the center on average will pass through $(N)^2$ intersections (will make on average $(N)^2$ steps) to leave the region containing $(N)^3$ nodes. The time to pass one step $\tau_1 = 1(\text{time to pass unit distance})/N$; time to leave the region of space of volume 1 from center 0:

$$t_0 = (N)^2 \cdot \tau_1 = N \cdot (\text{time to pass unit distance}).$$

For three-dimensional random walk on a lattice with step $(1/N)$, the average exit time $\langle t_X \rangle$ from point 0 through a thin infinite layer located at a fixed distance X units of distance along the x axis

(i.e., at $x = X \cdot (\text{unit of distance})$, where $X \gg (1/N)$), is proportional to N : $\langle t_X \rangle \propto N$. Hence the time to reach the absorbing plane in 3D (with x and infinite y and z)

$$\langle t_X \rangle = (X \cdot N)^2 \cdot \tau_1 = (X^2 \cdot N) \cdot (\text{time to pass unit distance}).$$

Let's estimate random walk in all random directions in space with fixed step $L = (\frac{1}{N})$ over fixed time τ_1 , which corresponds to speed $|\mathbf{v}| = 1$. The diffusion coefficient D for

such three-dimensional random walk is defined as:

$$D = \frac{(L)^2}{6\tau_1} = \frac{\left(\frac{1(\text{unit of distance})}{N}\right)^2}{6\frac{1(\text{time to pass unit distance})}{N}}$$

$$= \frac{1}{6N} \frac{(\text{unit of distance})^2}{(\text{time to pass unit distance})}.$$

The average time t_0 to exit from a sphere region of diameter 1 and $R = 1/2$ from center 0 for random walk with fixed step L is given by:

$$t_0 = \frac{R^2}{6D} = \frac{\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^2}{6\left(\frac{1}{6N}\right)} = \frac{N}{4} \cdot 1(\text{time to pass unit distance}).$$

For a sphere of volume 1 (radius $R \approx 0.62$) the exit time will be

$$t_0 \approx 0.38N \cdot 1(\text{time to pass unit distance}).$$

Let's define the average exit time $\langle t_X \rangle$ from point 0 through a thin infinite layer located at a fixed distance X units of distance along the x axis (i.e., at $x = X \cdot (\text{unit of distance})$, where X units of distance $\gg L$) for three-dimensional random walk in all random directions in space with fixed step L :

for one-dimensional projection of random walk along the x axis, the effective diffusion coefficient D_X equals:

$$D_X = \frac{(L)^2}{6\tau_1} = \frac{\left(\frac{1}{N}\right)^2}{6\left(\frac{1}{N}\right)} = \frac{L \cdot (\text{unit of distance})}{6 \cdot (\text{time to pass unit distance})},$$

since the steps are isotropic, and the step variance along one coordinate is one third of the total variance in three dimensions. Dimension $D_X \frac{(\text{unit of distance})^2}{(\text{time to pass unit distance})}$.

The average first passage time to a plane at distance X for Brownian motion in one dimension is estimated as:

$$\langle t_X \rangle = \frac{(X \cdot (\text{unit of distance}))^2}{2D_X} = \frac{3 \cdot (X)^2 \cdot |\mathbf{v}|}{L}.$$

If we imagine the motion of spherical matter waves between collisions, then in motion matter will create an intersection for itself and change directions at the point of next collision through some average distance between collisions L , which will be inversely proportional to the linear density of matter ρ in this region of space: $L = \frac{1}{\rho}$. Then a change in the linear density of matter ρ will lead to a change in the average area of all fronts of all waves propagating after collisions in a limited volume.

In such a case, we can single out one single matter vector exiting from the reference point (the ratio of number to differentially small area on the sphere of differential unit radius: $\rho^3 \cdot [dr]^3 \cdot \frac{ds}{4\pi \cdot [dr]^2}$) and depending on the linear density of matter ρ in this region, calculate some average distance L , through which it will be uniformly scattered in all directions due to the drop in "statistical weight" of its momentum in the total amount of matter with which it will collide on its path. This is a consequence of the statement that any vector will be completely uniformly distributed among all vectors exiting the collision only when colliding with an equal in modulus and oppositely directed vector. Such a distance L is extremely small and inversely proportional to the linear density of matter ρ .

2.4 Displacement Calculation and Time Effect

Collisions of matter fragments are modeled as random walks. Imagine the movement as if of a colored portion of matter, at the starting point, and by the density of coloring of space, trace where on average it ended up after a certain time. From the initial point, matter propagates in space as a normal distribution in three dimensions. After moving in space and the next collision, each part of the original portion will again begin to propagate as a normal distribution in three dimensions from the new point.

Let's relate the linear density ρ to the average distance between collisions L , thus defining the unit density through the unit length L : $\rho = \frac{1}{L}$.

Time between such collisions:

$$\tau = \frac{L}{|\mathbf{v}|} = \frac{1}{\rho |\mathbf{v}|}.$$

In a homogeneous medium $\rho = \rho_0$; $L_0 = \frac{1}{\rho_0}$; $\tau_0 = \frac{1}{\rho_0 |\mathbf{1}|}$, since $|\mathbf{v}| = 1$.

If the linear density changes along the x axis: $\rho(x) = \rho_0 + \frac{d\rho}{dx} \cdot x$, (denote further $\frac{d\rho}{dx} = \rho'_x$ - gradient directed along the x axis in m^{-2}), then the average time between collisions will change depending on the local linear density:

$$\tau_L(x) = \frac{1}{(\rho_0 + \rho'_x \cdot x) \cdot |\mathbf{1}|} = \frac{\rho_0}{(\rho_0 + \rho'_x \cdot x)} \cdot \tau_0; \quad \frac{\tau_L(x)}{\tau_0} = \frac{L_x}{L_0} = \frac{\rho_0}{(\rho_0 + \rho'_x \cdot x)}.$$

The selected portion of matter during observation time t moves within a sphere of radius $R = |\mathbf{1}| \cdot t$ from the observation starting point. Only a vector moving after each collision straight in the original direction can move away to such a radius. In a limited region of radius R , we consider the gradient of linear density $\frac{d\rho}{dx}$ (or ρ'_x) constant - this can be allowed on small scales, but this cannot be on macroscopic scales.

Changing density along one axis is analogous to changing the scale of the statistical model of random walk with fixed step in this direction.

$$L(x) = \frac{1}{(\rho_0 + \rho'_x \cdot x)}; \quad \tau_1(x) = \frac{1}{(\rho_0 + \rho'_x \cdot x) \cdot |\mathbf{1}|}; \quad N(x) = \frac{1}{L(x)} = (\rho_0 + \rho'_x \cdot x).$$

$$D(x) = \frac{L(x) \cdot (\text{unit of distance})}{6 \cdot (\text{time to pass unit distance})}$$

$$= \frac{1 \cdot (\text{unit of distance})}{6 \cdot (\rho_0 + \rho'_x \cdot x) \cdot (\text{time to pass unit distance})}.$$

Consider the simple case when matter on average is at rest (average momentum of matter in the region of space \mathbf{P} equals 0). Then any portion of matter, infinitely dividing, after each collision, exits in all directions with equal probability: along the x axis with average speed $|\mathbf{v}|/2 = 1/2$ for the hemisphere of vectors - both towards increasing density $\rho(x)$ and towards decreasing density $\rho(x)$ with probability $1/2$. The same is true for other axes y and z . The average exit speed $|\mathbf{v}|/2 = 1/2$ mathematically equals the modulus of the sum of all vectors of equal length over the hemisphere facing the selected direction in space.

In differential scales, immediately after exiting the collision, increasing density ρ in the direction $(+\rho'_x)$ leads to decreasing the average distance L until the next complete scattering along vectors, approaching the average level (X) of redistribution, where this matter will again divide in half and begin to move in different directions along the x axis.

Let's define the average removal L_m along the x axis of the point of complete scattering from the exit point from the origin 0, adding the average distances L_a from the exit point 0 to the point of complete scattering in each direction depending on the angle to the x axis: $a \in [0, \pi]$.

For point $x = dr \cdot \cos \theta$ the gradient effect is estimated at the midpoint of the path: $x = \frac{dr}{2} \cdot \cos \theta$:

$$\rho \left(\frac{dr}{2} \cos \theta \right) = \rho_0 + \rho'_x \cdot \left(\frac{dr}{2} \cos \theta \right).$$

For each separate direction:

$$L_a = \frac{1}{\rho_0 + \rho'_x \cdot \left(\frac{\cos a}{2} \right) \cdot L_a}; \quad \rho'_x \cdot \left(\frac{\cos a}{2} \right) \cdot L_a^2 + \rho_0 \cdot L_a - 1 = 0.$$

$$L_a = \frac{\pm (\rho_0^2 + 2 \cdot \rho'_x \cdot \cos a)^{\frac{1}{2}} - \rho_0}{\rho'_x \cdot \cos a}; \quad L_a = \frac{\pm \left(\left(\left(\frac{\rho_0^2}{\rho'_x \cdot \cos a} \right) + 1 \right)^2 - 1 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} - \left(\frac{\rho_0^2}{\rho'_x \cdot \cos a} \right)}{\rho_0}.$$

The solution with minus is unrealistic at $\lim \rho'_x \rightarrow 0$, hence:

$$\rho_0 \cdot L_a = \left(\left(1 + \left(\frac{\rho_0^2}{\rho'_x \cdot \cos a} \right) \right)^2 - 1 \right)^{1/2} - \frac{\rho_0^2}{\rho'_x \cdot \cos a}.$$

$$L_m = \langle L_a \rangle \approx \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \left(\frac{(\rho_0^2 + 2 \cdot \rho'_x \cdot \cos a)^{1/2} - \rho_0}{\rho'_x \cdot \cos a} \right) \cdot (\cos a \cdot \sin a \cdot da)$$

$$= \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \left(\frac{(\rho_0^2 + 2 \cdot \rho'_x \cdot \cos a)^{1/2} - \rho_0}{\rho'_x} \right) \cdot \sin a \cdot da.$$

$$L_{m+} = \frac{(\rho_0^2 + 2 \cdot \rho'_x)^{3/2} - \rho_0^3 - 3 \cdot \rho'_x \cdot \rho_0}{3 \cdot (\rho'_x)^2},$$

$$L_{m-} = \frac{(\rho_0^2 - 2 \cdot \rho'_x)^{3/2} - \rho_0^3 + 3 \cdot \rho'_x \cdot \rho_0}{3 \cdot (\rho'_x)^2}.$$

$$\lim_{\rho'_x \rightarrow 0} L_m = \frac{1}{2 \cdot \rho_0}.$$

Let's trace the motion of random walks exiting from the equilibrium collision point 0, one of which moves in the $+x$ direction, the other $-x$. At distances L_{m+} and L_{m-} along the x axis, on average they will reach the plane on which on average the next equilibrium collision occurs. The average time for the random walk to reach these boundaries from 0 differs: $t_{1(+)}$ and $t_{1(-)}$. At these levels, they will again be uniformly divided into all possible directions: half will begin returning to point 0 and will meet on the plane with coordinate X at time T , and the other half will continue to move away as random walks to their new boundaries $2L_{m+}$ and $2L_{m-}$.

Let's find the coordinate X of the plane where the returning parts will meet, and the total time T of this meeting from the very beginning of the calculation. At this coordinate should be the center of distribution of matter that exited from 0. This is the problem of exit from 0 and subsequent meeting of two random walks after reflection from boundaries L_{m+} and L_{m-} .

For isotropic 3D random walk with fixed step length L and speed $|\mathbf{v}| = |\mathbf{1}|$, the time of one step: $\tau = \frac{L}{|\mathbf{1}|}$, diffusion coefficient: $D = \frac{L \cdot |\mathbf{1}|}{6}$.

$$D_{(L_{m+})} = \frac{|\mathbf{1}|}{6 \cdot (\rho_0 + \rho'_x \cdot L_{m+})}; \quad D_{(L_{m-})} = \frac{|\mathbf{1}|}{6 \cdot (\rho_0 - \rho'_x \cdot L_{m-})}.$$

Average time to reach a plane at distance X : $\langle t_x \rangle = \frac{3 \cdot X^2}{L \cdot |\mathbf{1}|}$.

Average time to reach boundaries in a linearly inhomogeneous medium L_{m+} and L_{m-} :

$$t_{(+)} = 3\rho_0(L_{m+})^2 + 2\rho'_x(L_{m+})^3; \quad t_{(-)} = 3\rho_0(L_{m-})^2 - 2\rho'_x(L_{m-})^3.$$

The exact solution for the meeting coordinate X and time T requires solving a cubic equation, which is difficult to simplify analytically. However, for small density gradient ($|\rho'_x| \ll \rho_0$), approximate formulas can be obtained. Assume: $|\rho'_x| \ll \rho_0$. Expand L_{m+} , L_{m-} , $t_{(+)}$, $t_{(-)}$ in Taylor series, keeping terms up to first order in ρ'_x .

The reflection boundaries L_{m+} and L_{m-} are approximated as:

$$L_{m+} \approx \frac{1}{2 \cdot \rho_0} - \frac{\rho'_x}{8 \cdot \rho_0^3}, \quad L_{m-} \approx \frac{1}{2 \cdot \rho_0} + \frac{\rho'_x}{8 \cdot \rho_0^3}.$$

The times to reach boundaries are approximated as:

$$t1_{(+)} \approx \frac{3}{4 \cdot \rho_0} + \frac{\rho'_x}{4 \cdot \rho_0^3}, \quad t1_{(-)} \approx \frac{3}{4 \cdot \rho_0} - \frac{\rho'_x}{4 \cdot \rho_0^3}.$$

Motion time after reflection from boundaries L_{m+} and L_{m-} :

from L_{m+} towards 0 to the left: $t2_{(+)} \approx \frac{3}{4 \cdot \rho_0} + \frac{\rho'_x}{8 \cdot \rho_0^3} - 3X$,

from L_{m-} towards 0 to the right: $t2_{(-)} \approx \frac{3}{4 \cdot \rho_0} + \frac{\rho'_x}{8 \cdot \rho_0^3} + 3X$.

Meeting condition: $t1_{(+)} + t2_{(+)} = t1_{(-)} + t2_{(-)}$, hence

$$\frac{3}{2 \cdot \rho_0} + \frac{3 \cdot \rho'_x}{8 \cdot \rho_0^3} - 3X = \frac{3}{2 \cdot \rho_0} + 3X.$$

Solving for X :

$$X \approx \frac{\rho'_x}{16 \cdot \rho_0^3}.$$

Substitute X into the expression for $t1_{(+)} + t2_{(+)}$:

$$T \approx \frac{3}{2 \cdot \rho_0} + \frac{3 \cdot \rho'_x}{16 \cdot \rho_0^3} = \frac{24 \cdot \rho_0^2 + 3 \cdot \rho'_x}{16 \cdot \rho_0^3}.$$

Meeting coordinate X and time T (from start of motion 0) for small ρ'_x ($|\rho'_x| \ll \rho_0$):

$$X \approx \frac{\rho'_x}{16 \cdot \rho_0^3}, \quad T \approx \frac{3}{2 \cdot \rho_0}.$$

The meeting time T includes time to boundaries $t1_{(+)}$ and $t1_{(-)}$, and motion after reflection and accounts for the change in $D_{(x)}$ when moving towards each other. The displacement of the meeting point X is due to the asymmetry of diffusion coefficients. If $\rho'_x > 0$, the density of the medium increases with x . A particle in the positive region moves

slower, so the meeting shifts towards positive X . At $\rho'_x = 0$ the medium is homogeneous, and the meeting occurs at the origin ($X = 0$) at moment $T = \frac{3}{2 \cdot \rho_0}$.

When considering the result of this calculation, it should be taken into account that during time T , equal to the average time of movement along the x axis from 0 to L_m and back, only half of the matter will return to coordinate X , while the other half will all this time be moving away on average from 0. To obtain the position of all the original matter, we must take the time only for one average step ($T/2$), considering that during this time half of the matter moves along the x axis from 0 in different directions, and the other half at the same time moves from L_{m+} and L_{m-} towards each other to 0. Thus, for the average time of one movement along the x axis: $T = \frac{3}{4 \cdot \rho_0 |\mathbf{v}|}$ we track the movement of all the original matter along the x axis completely, taking into account both phases of movement simultaneously.

The speed of displacement along the x axis of the center of matter distribution:

$$U = X/(T/2) = \frac{\rho'_x |\mathbf{v}|}{12 \cdot \rho_0^2}$$

The levels L_{m+} and L_{m-} are not distances of one step, which we defined as $L_a = \frac{1}{\rho_0 + \rho'_x \cdot \left(\frac{\cos \alpha}{2}\right) \cdot L_a}$. The levels L_{m+} and L_{m-} characterize the difference between the distances from which equal shares of matter will split in half, turn around and return to the center, while the other half of the matter will continue to move away from 0 with speed $|\mathbf{v}|/2$. Similarly, the time $T/2$ is not the time of one step τ_1 .

The displacement H over the time of one step τ_1 between 0 and the next complete scattering is determined by the speed U :

$$H = \frac{\rho'_x}{12 \cdot \rho_0^3}$$

Over time $\tau_1 = \frac{1}{\rho_0 |\mathbf{1}|}$ respectively, the acceleration g of the matter portion from 0 equals:

$$\mathbf{g} = \frac{\rho'_x |\mathbf{v}|^2}{6 \cdot \rho_0}$$

Accelerating after equilibrium exit from collision to the next equilibrium collision, matter gains momentum. All matter in the density gradient shifts equally and all extremely small displacements add up to the total acceleration of matter in the selected volume of space. At the same time, for the interacting matter as a whole, these processes are balanced in directions and the total momentum, of course, is unchanged.

The formula $g = \frac{V^2}{6} \cdot \frac{dP}{P}$ is derived as acceleration by density gradient, analogous to attraction.

2.5 Cluster Equilibrium Model

2.5.1 Scattering Speed and Acceleration

Let's trace the motion of matter from a point located at distance R from the center of the matter accumulation.

In classical mechanics, centrifugal acceleration: $a_{\text{centrifugal}} = \frac{v^2}{R}$.

Consider the speed of removal of matter exiting from point O on the sphere, from the straight line of the radius from the center to this point.

On a sphere of radius R there is point O . From this point, particles exit in all directions in space with constant speed modulus v . The particles move as three-dimensional random walk with average distance l between collisions. Let's find the average speed of removal of these particles from the straight line passing through the center of the sphere and point O (i.e., from the radius).

Problem in Cylindrical Coordinates Introduce a cylindrical coordinate system (ρ, ϕ, z) , where:

The Z axis coincides with the given radius (straight line passing through the center of the sphere and point O),

ρ is the distance from the particle to the Z axis,

ϕ is the azimuthal angle,

z is the coordinate along the Z axis.

The speed of removal from the radius is determined by the radial component of velocity in cylindrical coordinates:

$$v_\rho = \frac{d\rho}{dt}.$$

Our goal is to find the average value of the modulus of this speed: $\langle |v_\rho| \rangle$.

Expression for v_ρ through velocity and position angles The velocity vector of a particle in Cartesian coordinates:

$$\vec{v} = (v_x, v_y, v_z).$$

In spherical coordinates associated with the velocity direction:

$$v_x = v \sin \theta \cos \psi, \quad v_y = v \sin \theta \sin \psi, \quad v_z = v \cos \theta,$$

where:

θ is the angle between velocity and the Z axis ($0 \leq \theta \leq \pi$),

ψ is the azimuthal angle of velocity ($0 \leq \psi \leq 2\pi$).

In cylindrical coordinates, the radial component of velocity is expressed as:

$$v_\rho = \frac{xv_x + yv_y}{\rho} = v_x \cos \phi + v_y \sin \phi,$$

where ϕ is the azimuthal angle of the particle's position. Substituting v_x and v_y :

$$v_\rho = v \sin \theta (\cos \psi \cos \phi + \sin \psi \sin \phi) = v \sin \theta \cos(\psi - \phi).$$

Thus,

$$v_\rho = v \sin \theta \cos \alpha, \quad \text{where } \alpha = \psi - \phi.$$

Averaging over velocity directions and position For isotropic random walk:

The angle θ is distributed with probability density $\frac{1}{2} \sin \theta$ (normalized on $[0, \pi]$).

The angles ψ and ϕ are uniformly distributed on $[0, 2\pi]$ and independent.

The difference $\alpha = \psi - \phi$ is also uniformly distributed on $[0, 2\pi]$.

The average value of the modulus of radial velocity:

$$\langle |v_\rho| \rangle = \langle |v \sin \theta \cos \alpha| \rangle = v \cdot \langle |\sin \theta| \rangle \cdot \langle |\cos \alpha| \rangle,$$

since θ and α are independent.

Calculation of average values

Average $\langle |\sin \theta| \rangle$:

$$\langle |\sin \theta| \rangle = \int_0^\pi |\sin \theta| \cdot \frac{1}{2} \sin \theta d\theta = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^\pi \sin^2 \theta d\theta.$$

Using the identity $\sin^2 \theta = \frac{1 - \cos(2\theta)}{2}$:

$$\int_0^\pi \sin^2 \theta d\theta = \int_0^\pi \frac{1 - \cos(2\theta)}{2} d\theta = \frac{1}{2} \left[\theta - \frac{\sin(2\theta)}{2} \right]_0^\pi = \frac{\pi}{2}.$$

Consequently,

$$\langle |\sin \theta| \rangle = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{\pi}{2} = \frac{\pi}{4}.$$

Average $\langle |\cos \alpha| \rangle$:

$$\langle |\cos \alpha| \rangle = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} |\cos \alpha| d\alpha.$$

Considering symmetry:

$$\int_0^{2\pi} |\cos \alpha| d\alpha = 4 \int_0^{\pi/2} \cos \alpha d\alpha = 4 [\sin \alpha]_0^{\pi/2} = 4.$$

Consequently,

$$\langle |\cos \alpha| \rangle = \frac{4}{2\pi} = \frac{2}{\pi}.$$

Result Substituting the computed averages:

$$\langle |v_\rho| \rangle = v \cdot \frac{\pi}{4} \cdot \frac{2}{\pi} = \frac{v}{2}.$$

The average speed of removal of particles from the radius in three-dimensional random walk equals:

$$\boxed{\frac{v}{2}}$$

The result $\frac{v}{2}$ shows that on average particles move away from the radius with speed equal to half of their full speed v .

The value l (average distance between collisions) does not affect the answer, since the isotropy of random walk preserves the average value of $|v_\rho|$ at each step.

Unlike rectilinear motion (where the average removal speed is $\frac{\pi}{4}v \approx 0.785v$), in random walk the velocity directions constantly change, and only part of the perpendicular component of velocity effectively increases the distance to the axis.

Acceleration:

$$a_{\text{scattering}} = \frac{(|\mathbf{v}|/2)^2}{R} = \frac{|\mathbf{v}|^2}{4R}$$

counteracts compression of the accumulation, decreasing with increasing R .

2.5.2 Acceleration by Density Gradient

The acceleration \mathbf{g} acting on matter in a stationary cluster is determined by the density gradient:

$$\mathbf{g} = \frac{|\mathbf{v}|^2}{6} \cdot \frac{d\rho}{dR}.$$

Equating

$$\mathbf{g} = \frac{|\mathbf{v}|^2}{6} \cdot \frac{d\rho}{dR} = \frac{|\mathbf{v}|^2}{4R},$$

we determine: the linear density $\rho_{(R)}$ of a stationary stable spherical accumulation of matter around point 0:

$$\rho_{(R)} = \frac{\rho_{(1)}}{R^{1.5}},$$

where $\rho_{(1)}$ is the linear density at distance $R = 1$ from the center of the cluster, and ρ characterizes the amount of matter per unit length along the radial direction.

$$\frac{d\rho}{dR} = \frac{d}{dR} \left(\frac{\rho_{(1)}}{R^{1.5}} \right) = \rho_{(1)} \cdot \left(-\frac{3}{2} R^{-2.5} \right) = -\frac{3\rho_{(1)}}{2R^{2.5}}.$$

Substitute into the formula:

$$\mathbf{g} = \frac{|\mathbf{v}|^2}{6} \cdot \frac{-\frac{3\rho_{(1)}}{2R^{2.5}}}{\frac{\rho_{(1)}}{R^{1.5}}} = \frac{|\mathbf{v}|^2}{6} \cdot \left(-\frac{3}{2} \cdot \frac{R^{1.5}}{R^{2.5}} \right) = \frac{|\mathbf{v}|^2}{6} \cdot \left(-\frac{3}{2R} \right) = -\frac{|\mathbf{v}|^2}{4R}.$$

Dimension $[\mathbf{g}] = [l/t^2]$, the negative sign indicates direction towards the center.

The $R^{-1.5}$ dependence reflects the decrease of linear density with distance, which agrees with the balance between expansion and compression.

2.6 Density Distribution Near the Cluster Center

One of the key tasks of the model is to describe the behavior of density near the center of the cluster. The original function $\rho_{(R)} = \frac{\rho_{(1)}}{R^{1.5}}$ predicts infinite growth of density at $R \rightarrow 0$, which is physically unrealistic. Moreover, the gradient $\frac{d\rho}{dR} = -\frac{3\rho_{(1)}}{2R^{2.5}}$ becomes extremely steep near the center, indicating nonlinear dependence and change of gradient direction in space. Simple statistics are not applicable here: in the immediate vicinity of the start of matter motion, its trajectories create self-obstacles, especially pronounced closer to the center. This limits the growth of density, forming a finite peak resembling the top of a normal distribution. We propose a modified density function and analyze it approximately.

2.6.1 Proposed Density Function

To eliminate the singularity and account for self-regulation, we introduce the function:

$$\rho_{(R)} = \rho_{(1)} \cdot \left(\frac{R_0}{R + R_0} \right)^{1.5},$$

where ρ_0 is the finite density at the center ($R = 0$), R_0 is the core radius parameter smoothing the distribution.

2.6.2 Properties:

At the center ($R = 0$):

$$\rho_{(0)} = \rho_{(1)} \cdot \left(\frac{R_0}{0 + R_0} \right)^{1.5} = \rho_{(1)},$$

density is finite, singularity is eliminated.

At large distances ($R \gg R_0$): $\rho_{(R)} \approx \frac{\rho_{(1)}}{R^{1.5}}$.

The function continuously decreases from $\rho_0 = \rho_{(1)}$ to $\frac{\rho_{(1)}}{R^{1.5}}$.

2.6.3 Gradient:

$$\frac{d\rho}{dR} = -\frac{3 \cdot \rho_{(1)} \cdot R_0^{1.5}}{2 \cdot (R + R_0)^{2.5}}.$$

At $R = 0$: $\frac{d\rho}{dR} = -\frac{1.5 \cdot \rho_{(1)}}{R_0}$, finite value.

At large R : $\frac{d\rho}{dR} \approx -\frac{1.5 \cdot \rho_{(1)}}{R^{2.5}}$, as in the original model.

2.6.4 Curvature (second derivative):

$$\frac{d^2\rho}{dR^2} = \frac{3.75 \cdot \rho_{(1)} \cdot R_0^{1.5}}{(R + R_0)^{3.5}}.$$

At $R = 0$: $\frac{d^2\rho}{dR^2} = \frac{3.75\rho_{(1)}}{R_0^2} > 0$. At $R = 0$ the second derivative $\frac{d^2\rho}{dR^2} > 0$, which together with the monotonic decrease of the function $\rho_{(R)}$ means that the function is convex downward, and its greatest value is at the left boundary of the domain, at point $R = 0$. As R increases, the curvature decreases, the gradient smoothens.

2.6.5 Physical Interpretation

Observing any portion of matter at distance R from the center, imagine that this matter emanates from all points of a sphere of radius R . The trajectories of the tracked portion of matter moving towards the center intersect with themselves more often than at large R : the area of the sphere $4\pi R^2$ decreases, and the density of flows increases. This creates self-obstacles of trajectories, which partially replace themselves the density of surrounding matter in the statistics of collisions, and passing through the center, move "towards themselves". It can be figuratively said that closer to the center, matter statistically begins to collide with itself more often than it should, partially replacing for itself the gradient of linear density. The smaller R , the stronger the effect, which limits the density to the value $\rho_{(0)}$. The sum $(R + R_0)$ in the denominator reflects this smoothing, preventing infinite growth.

Initially, $\rho_{(1)}$ was proposed as the linear density at distance $R=1$ from the center of a stationary matter accumulation, but the need to change the density function with radius equates this density to the maximum in the center of the cluster $\rho_{(0)}$, which also requires changing to $\rho_{(0)}$ the designation of linear density in the function:

$$\rho_{(R)} = \rho_{(0)} \cdot \left(\frac{R_0}{R + R_0} \right)^{1.5}.$$

2.6.6 Approximation Near the Center

Expand $\rho_{(R)}$ in Taylor series at $R \rightarrow 0$:

$$\rho_{(R)} = \rho_{(0)} \cdot \left(1 + \frac{R}{R_0}\right)^{-1.5} \approx \rho_{(0)} \cdot \left(1 - 1.5 \frac{R}{R_0} + 1.875 \frac{R^2}{R_0^2}\right).$$

Compare with normal distribution $\rho_{(0)} \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{R^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) \approx \rho_{(0)} \cdot \left(1 - \frac{R^2}{2\sigma^2}\right)$. The quadratic term $1.875 \frac{R^2}{R_0^2}$ gives $\sigma^2 = \frac{R_0^2}{3.75}$, indicating similarity to a Gaussian peak, although the linear term shows deviation from pure normality.

2.6.7 Acceleration

The acceleration associated with the gradient:

$$\mathbf{g} = \frac{|\mathbf{v}|^2}{6} \cdot \frac{-\frac{3\rho_{(0)}}{2R^{2.5}}}{\frac{\rho_{(0)}}{R^{1.5}}} = \frac{|\mathbf{v}|^2}{6} \cdot \frac{-\frac{1.5 \cdot R_0^{1.5} \rho_{(0)}}{(R+R_0)^{2.5}}}{\rho_{(0)} \cdot \left(\frac{R_0}{R+R_0}\right)^{1.5}} = -\frac{|\mathbf{v}|^2}{4(R+R_0)}.$$

At $R = 0$: $\mathbf{g} = -\frac{|\mathbf{v}|^2}{4R_0}$ finite. Actually at the center $\mathbf{g} = 0$, but this deviation is a result of simplification.

At large R : $\mathbf{g} \approx -\frac{|\mathbf{v}|^2}{4R}$, as in the previous section.

2.6.8 Conclusion

The modified density $\rho_{(R)} = \rho_{(0)} \cdot \left(\frac{R_0}{R+R_0}\right)^{1.5}$ eliminates the singularity, reaching a peak $\rho_{(0)}$ at the center and transitioning to $R^{-1.5}$ at large distances. Self-obstacles near the center, caused by convergence of trajectories, form a finite profile close to the top of a normal distribution with approximate variance $\sigma^2 = \frac{R_0^2}{3.75}$. This agrees with the cluster equilibrium, where the collision frequency $\nu(R) \propto \rho(R)$.

2.7 Characteristic Diameter of Accumulation

We investigate the existence of a diameter D at which the time of passage of a matter wave through the center equals the time of its motion along a semicircle of diameter D . This condition of dynamic equilibrium between radial and tangential propagation processes.

2.7.1 Wave Process Speed

The wave speed depends on local density:

$$v(R) = \frac{|\mathbf{v}|}{2} \cdot \frac{\rho_{(D/2)}}{\rho_{(R)}}$$

where $\frac{|\mathbf{v}|}{2}$ is the maximum speed, $\rho_{(D/2)}$ is the density at the cluster boundary.

2.7.2 Density Model

We use the modified density function:

$$\rho_{(R)} = \rho_{(0)} \cdot \left(\frac{R_0}{R+R_0}\right)^{1.5}, \quad \rho_{(D/2)} = \rho_{(0)} \cdot \left(\frac{R_0}{D/2+R_0}\right)^{1.5}$$

2.7.3 Time of Passage Through Center

The wave travels distance D through the center with variable speed:

$$T_{\text{diam}} = \int_{-D/2}^{D/2} \frac{dR}{v(R)} = 2 \int_0^{D/2} \frac{dR}{v(R)}$$

$$T_{\text{diam}} = \frac{4}{|\mathbf{v}| \cdot \rho_{(D/2)}} \int_0^{D/2} \rho_{(R)} dR$$

2.7.4 Time of Motion Along Semicircle

Path length: $L = \pi \cdot \frac{D}{2}$, speed is constant:

$$v_{\text{circ}} = \frac{|\mathbf{v}|}{2}, \quad T_{\text{circ}} = \frac{L}{v_{\text{circ}}} = \frac{\pi D}{|\mathbf{v}|}$$

2.7.5 Equilibrium Equation

Equate the times:

$$T_{\text{diam}} = T_{\text{circ}}$$

$$\frac{4}{\rho_{(D/2)}} \int_0^{D/2} \rho_{(R)} dR = \pi D$$

2.7.6 Integral Calculation

$$\int_0^{D/2} \rho_{(R)} dR = \rho_{(0)} \cdot R_0^{1.5} \int_0^{D/2} (R + R_0)^{-1.5} dR$$

$$= 2\rho_{(0)} \cdot R_0 \cdot \left(1 - \left(\frac{R_0}{D/2 + R_0} \right)^{0.5} \right)$$

2.7.7 Main Equation

Substitute into the equilibrium equation:

$$\frac{8R_0 \cdot \left(1 - \left(\frac{R_0}{D/2 + R_0} \right)^{0.5} \right)}{\left(\frac{R_0}{D/2 + R_0} \right)^{1.5}} = \pi D$$

Introduce the dimensionless variable $x = \frac{D}{2R_0}$:

$$4(x + 1)^{1.5} \cdot (1 - (x + 1)^{-0.5}) = \pi x$$

$$4(x + 1)^{1.5} - 4(x + 1) = \pi x$$

2.7.8 Numerical Solution

Solve the equation $4(x + 1)^{1.5} - (\pi + 4)x - 4 = 0$:

$$x \approx 1.27, \quad D = 2xR_0 \approx 2.54R_0$$

2.7.9 Conclusion

The characteristic diameter of a stable matter accumulation is $D \approx 2.54R_0$. At this diameter, the time of wave propagation through the center of the cluster equals the time of its propagation along the boundary, which indicates dynamic equilibrium between radial and tangential processes and may determine the size of a stable cluster.

2.8 Cluster Mass

The total mass of the cluster is computed by integrating the volume density over all space. Using the density model $\rho(R) = \rho_{(0)} \cdot \left(\frac{R_0}{R+R_0}\right)^{1.5}$, we get the volume density:

$$\rho_V(R) = [\rho(R)]^3 = \rho_{(0)}^3 \cdot \left(\frac{R_0}{R+R_0}\right)^{4.5}$$

Cluster mass:

$$M = \int \rho_V(R) dV = 4\pi\rho_{(0)}^3 \int_0^\infty R^2 \cdot \left(\frac{R_0}{R+R_0}\right)^{4.5} dR$$

After variable substitution $x = R/R_0$ and integral computation:

$$M = \frac{64\pi}{105}\rho_{(0)}^3 R_0^3$$

This result shows that the total mass of the cluster is finite and determined by the parameters $\rho_{(0)}$ and R_0 , characterizing the matter distribution in the center and the size of the cluster core respectively.

2.9 Attraction Force of Spherical Shell to Center

In the proposed model, there is no force in the classical understanding as a long-range interaction. Instead, we consider statistical patterns of matter movement and its collisions that create an effect analogous to force action.

Based on the balance of momenta in the statistical model, the attraction force of a spherical shell to the center is defined as:

$$F(R) = g(R) \cdot [\rho(R)]^2 \cdot S(R)$$

where: - $g(R) = -\frac{|v|^2}{4(R+R_0)}$ - acceleration due to density gradient - $\rho(R) = \rho_0 \cdot \left(\frac{R_0}{R+R_0}\right)^{1.5}$ - linear density - $S(R) = 4\pi R^2$ - area of spherical surface

Substituting the expressions, we get:

$$F(R) = -\pi|v|^2\rho_0^2R_0^3 \cdot \frac{R^2}{(R+R_0)^4}$$

This formula describes the effective attraction of a spherical shell to the center of the cluster, arising as a result of statistical displacement of matter in the direction of the density gradient.

3 Interaction of Two Accumulations

3.1 Interaction of Identical Accumulations

This chapter investigates the interaction of two identical density accumulations located at a certain distance from each other, through a surface separating their density fields. Two identical accumulations with parameter m are considered, connected by a segment, through the midpoint of which a normal plane is drawn. This plane serves as a boundary on which the density gradient in projection onto the axis connecting the accumulation centers is zero, which prevents unbalanced matter flow. It should be noted immediately that for two different accumulations, the surface separating them should be constructed on the same principle of absence of unbalanced matter flow from one accumulation to the other through the separating calculated surface, and this is possible only when the projection of the density gradient onto the normal to the calculated surface is zero.

The goal is to compute the interaction force of one accumulation with the field of the other through this separating plane. For this, the density and acceleration at a point on the plane are determined, after which the force flux is integrated over the entire surface.

Consider two accumulations with centers at points M_1 and M_2 , at distance r from each other. The linear density of each accumulation at $R = 1$ is m . The separation plane passes through the midpoint of segment M_1M_2 and is perpendicular to it. At point A on this plane:

$$\rho_A = \frac{m}{\left(\frac{r/2}{\cos a}\right)^{1.5}} = \frac{m \cos^{1.5} a}{\left(\frac{r}{2}\right)^{1.5}}$$

$$g_A = \frac{|\mathbf{v}|^2}{4\left(\frac{r/2}{\cos a}\right)} = \frac{|\mathbf{v}|^2 \cos a}{2r}$$

where a is the angle determining the interaction geometry.

Integral of force flux through the plane:

$$S = \int_0^{\pi/2} \left(\frac{8m^2 \cos^3 a}{r^3} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{|\mathbf{v}|^2 \cos^2 a}{2r} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{\pi r^2}{2} \cdot \frac{\sin a}{\cos^3 a} \right) da = \frac{2\pi |\mathbf{v}|^2 m^2}{3r^2}$$

Thus, the attraction force between accumulations:

$$F = \frac{2\pi |\mathbf{v}|^2 m^2}{3r^2}$$

3.2 Interaction of Different Accumulations

In this section, we explore in detail the interaction of two wave accumulations with different parameters, such as m_1 and m_2 , which can be interpreted as mass analogs in our model. These accumulations are located at distance r from each other, and their interaction occurs through a special surface, which we denote S .

3.2.1 Description of Accumulations and Their Density

Imagine two wave accumulations - A and B , whose centers are at points \mathbf{c}_1 and \mathbf{c}_2 . Distance between centers:

$$r = |\mathbf{c}_2 - \mathbf{c}_1|$$

Each accumulation is described by a linear density function:

$$\rho_i(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{m_i}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{c}_i|^{1.5}}, \quad i = 1, 2,$$

where: - \mathbf{x} - coordinates of an arbitrary point in space, - \mathbf{c}_i - center of the i -th accumulation, - m_i - accumulation parameter ("mass analog"), - $|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{c}_i|$ - distance from point \mathbf{x} to center \mathbf{c}_i .

3.2.2 Definition of Interaction Surface

Find the gradient $\rho_i(\mathbf{x})$. For function $\rho_i(\mathbf{x}) = m_i |\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{c}_i|^{-1.5}$:

$$\nabla \rho_i(\mathbf{x}) = -\frac{1.5m_i}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{c}_i|^{2.5}} \cdot \frac{\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{c}_i}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{c}_i|}$$

Gradient modulus:

$$|\nabla \rho_i(\mathbf{x})| = \frac{1.5m_i}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{c}_i|^{2.5}}$$

Define the surface S from the condition of equality of gradient moduli:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1.5m_1}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{c}_1|^{2.5}} &= \frac{1.5m_2}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{c}_2|^{2.5}} \\ \frac{m_1}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{c}_1|^{2.5}} &= \frac{m_2}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{c}_2|^{2.5}} \\ \left(\frac{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{c}_1|}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{c}_2|} \right)^{2.5} &= \frac{m_1}{m_2} \end{aligned}$$

This equation describes the surface S .

3.2.3 Formulation of Interaction Force

The attraction force between accumulations is defined as an integral over surface S :

$$F = m_1 m_2 \int_S \frac{1}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{c}_1|^{1.5} |\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{c}_2|^{1.5}} dS$$

For large distances, the force takes the form:

$$F \approx \frac{2\pi |\mathbf{v}|^2 m_1 m_2}{3r^2}$$

3.2.4 Computation of Surface Integral

Consider an example: $m_1 = 1$, $m_2 = 2$, $r = 1$, $\mathbf{c}_1 = (0, 0, 0)$, $\mathbf{c}_2 = (1, 0, 0)$, $|\mathbf{v}| = 1$.

Surface equation:

$$|\mathbf{x}|^{2.5} = \frac{1}{2} |\mathbf{x} - (1, 0, 0)|^{2.5}$$

Approximate S by plane $x = 0.365$.

Compute the integral:

$$I = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{1}{|\mathbf{x}|^{1.5} |\mathbf{x} - (1, 0, 0)|^{1.5}} dy dz,$$

where $\mathbf{x} = (0.365, y, z)$.

After transition to polar coordinates and numerical integration, we get $I \approx 2.135$. Then:

$$F = m_1 m_2 I = 1 \cdot 2 \cdot 2.135 \approx 4.27.$$

3.2.5 Comparison with Analytical Result

Analytical formula:

$$F = \frac{2\pi|\mathbf{v}|^2 m_1 m_2}{3r^2} = \frac{2\pi \cdot 1 \cdot 2 \cdot 1^2}{3 \cdot 1^2} = \frac{4\pi}{3} \approx 4.1888.$$

The difference is about 2%, which confirms the correctness of the model.

3.3 Physical Interpretation of Interaction Force

The expression for the interaction force between two wave accumulations:

$$F = \frac{2\pi|\mathbf{v}|^2 m_1 m_2}{3r^2}$$

can be interpreted as an attraction force, analogous to gravitational force in classical mechanics. Here m_1 and m_2 are accumulation parameters that we called mass analogs, $|\mathbf{v}|$ is the characteristic speed of matter wave propagation, and r is the distance between accumulation centers.

3.3.1 Role of Parameter m as Mass Analog

Note that m enters the formula quadratically ($m_1 m_2$) exactly like mass in Newton's law of attraction $F = G \frac{M_1 M_2}{r^2}$. This is not accidental. In our model, the linear density $\rho_i(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{m_i}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{c}_i|^{1.5}}$ determines how matter is distributed around the accumulation center. The larger m_i , the higher the density near the center, and the stronger the accumulation influences the surrounding space.

3.3.2 Gravity as Contact of Accumulation Boundaries

Gravitational interaction in this model can be viewed as a result of contact of boundaries of two wave accumulations through surface S , where the density gradients are balanced. Each accumulation is infinite in the sense that its density $\rho_i(\mathbf{x})$ decreases with distance but never becomes zero. This means that waves from one accumulation penetrate the region of the other, and their interaction occurs not at one point but over the entire surface S .

3.3.3 Comparison of Gravity with Modulated Waves

However, gravity is only a weak component of interaction. On surface S , the values of densities ρ_1 and ρ_2 and their gradients are small, since S is far from the accumulation centers (at large r). This makes gravity tens of orders of magnitude weaker than other possible interactions, such as modulated density waves.

Modulated waves are waves with asymmetric profile that arise in complex cyclic processes inside a limited volume. Such waves do not carry density on average if there is no counter interaction, but only oscillate around some average radius. These oscillations superimpose on the entire space of the other accumulation, creating a stronger interaction than simple density decrease.

3.3.4 Hypothesis on Origin of Charges

Imagine that charge fields arise from the separation of a single neutral wave structure. Initially, around a common center, there exist cyclic processes creating two types of density profiles: one with crests outward, the other inward. Under strong central collision or under the action of an external field, this structure splits into two particles with opposite profiles.

4 Matter Field

4.1 Transition from Modeling Matter Motion as Infinitely Small Particles to Modeling Matter Field

Let's move to a model of a continuous matter field, where space is homogeneously filled with an infinitely divisible substance. Unlike models with discrete particles, here there are no distinguished objects - matter is represented as a continuous substance, and its motion is determined by interaction with the surrounding field through an infinite number of collisions.

The idea of infinite divisibility of matter portions means that at each point \mathbf{x} the field \mathbf{M} simultaneously "splits" in all directions. This makes \mathbf{F} an integral over all possible ω , which replaces the discrete collision event with a continuous process.

4.2 Dynamics of Motion

4.2.1 Discrete Approach: Particle Motion

Particle motion is determined by stochastic equations. For each particle:

$$d\mathbf{x}_i(t) = \mathbf{v}_i(t)dt,$$

where $\mathbf{v}_i(t)$ is updated at collisions.

4.2.2 Continuous Approach: Field Evolution

The dynamics of the field $\mathbf{M}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is described by a partial differential equation:

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{M}}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{v} \otimes \mathbf{M}) = \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{M}, \nabla \mathbf{M}),$$

where $\mathbf{v} \otimes \mathbf{M}$ is the flux tensor, and \mathbf{F} is the term modeling continuous interactions. The mass conservation equation:

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{v}) = 0$$

4.3 Collisions and Interactions

4.3.1 Discrete Approach: Discrete Collisions

Consider the collision of two particles with fluxes $\mathbf{M}_1 = \rho_1 \mathbf{v}_1 \Delta V$ and $\mathbf{M}_2 = \rho_2 \mathbf{v}_2 \Delta V$. Momentum conservation:

$$\mathbf{P} = \mathbf{M}_1 + \mathbf{M}_2,$$

mass conservation:

$$M = |\mathbf{M}_1| + |\mathbf{M}_2|.$$

After collision, matter is distributed over a spherical surface:

$$\sigma(\vec{n}, t) = \frac{M}{4\pi [v(t - t_0)]^2} \cdot \frac{|\beta|}{4\pi \sinh |\beta|} \cdot e^{\vec{\beta} \cdot \vec{n}}$$

4.3.2 Continuous Approach: Continuous Interactions

In the continuous model, collisions are built into \mathbf{F} :

$$\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{M}, \nabla \mathbf{M}) = \int_{\Omega} \left[\frac{\rho}{4\pi} + \frac{3|\mathbf{M}|}{4\pi|\mathbf{v}|} (\omega \cdot \mathbf{e}_M) \right] |\mathbf{v}| \omega d\omega,$$

where Ω is the unit sphere, $\mathbf{e}_M = \frac{\mathbf{M}}{|\mathbf{M}|}$.

4.4 Displacement in Density Gradient

4.4.1 Discrete Approach: Particle Drift

Assume a density gradient $\rho(x) = \rho_0 + \frac{d\rho}{dx}x$. Particles collide more often in regions with larger ρ , which shifts their center of mass:

$$\langle x \rangle = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N x_i(t).$$

The drift speed depends on the collision frequency, proportional to ρ .

4.4.2 Continuous Approach: Field Acceleration

For field $\rho(\mathbf{x}, t)$ with gradient $\nabla \rho$:

$$\frac{d\langle \mathbf{x} \rangle}{dt} = \int \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}, t) \rho(\mathbf{x}, t) d\mathbf{x},$$

where $\mathbf{u} \propto \nabla \rho$. Acceleration:

$$\mathbf{g} = \frac{d^2 \langle \mathbf{x} \rangle}{dt^2} \propto \nabla \rho.$$

4.5 Interaction of Accumulations

4.5.1 Discrete Approach: Force Between Particles

For two accumulations with masses m_1, m_2 , the force is computed through flux integral:

$$F = \frac{2\pi|\mathbf{v}|^2 m_1 m_2}{3r^2}$$

4.5.2 Continuous Approach: Force Through Field

For fields ρ_1, ρ_2 , the force is an integral over surface S :

$$F = \int_S \rho_1 \rho_2 dS \approx \frac{2\pi|\mathbf{v}|^2 m_1 m_2}{3r^2}$$

4.6 Conclusion

We have shown the transition from a discrete particle model to a continuous field, preserving key properties such as gravitational force $F \propto r^{-2}$. The proposed model interprets gravity as a result of interaction of flows of a continuous matter field through equilibrium surfaces of gradients. The absence of fluctuations is achieved due to the infinite divisibility of portions and their motion along all possible paths, which replaces randomness with deterministic averaging.